

Determinants of Post Stroke Quality of Life: Experiences from a Physiotherapy Unit Clinic, South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

Introduction: Stroke is a prevalent cardiovascular system event particularly among people of African descent anywhere in the world. The impact of stroke on the life of survivors is multifaceted affecting their quality of physical, mental and social life. In the last four decades, studies reveal that stroke incidence in low- and middle-income countries such as Nigeria have witnessed a double increment in incidence whereas in high-income countries this has declined by over 40% within the same time period. This study aimed to examine the quality of life of stroke survivors in Nigeria and understand the factors that contribute to good quality of life among them.

Materials and Methods: In this descriptive cross-sectional study, participants were recruited during physical rehabilitation sessions at two tertiary hospitals in South-South Nigeria. Exclusion criteria included, prior transient ischemic heart attack, recurrent persistent deficit, underlying psychotic and mental disorders, cognitive impairment and those who were handicapped before the stroke event. Tools used for the study were a semi-structured questionnaire and the Stroke Impact Scale (SIS 3.0) which measured the quality of life among stroke survivors. Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results: Most of the respondents (54%) fell within the 56-65 years age group with mean age at 59.0 (SD = ± 9.12). The proportion of the average raw score to the total raw score of all the domains and total quality of life score were all above 50%. The emotions domain had the highest proportion of average to highest possible scores (91%). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) between, socioeconomic and demographic factors, clinical factors and home care on the quality of life of the stroke participants were done to find their association. Age ($F = 4.9$ ($P = 0.001$)) and marital status ($F = 4.28$ ($P = 0.007$)) the side of lesion ($F = 8.17$; $P = 0.005$), having a previous stroke ($F = 8.08$ ($P = 0.005$)), the type of stroke ($F = 11.37$; $P = 0.001$) and all aspects of the at home care with the exception of the hospital payment ($F = 1.73$; $L P = 0.165$) were significantly associated with quality of life. Gender $F = 3.54$ ($P = 0.070$) and employment status $F = 4.28$; $P = 0.137$), diabetes and hypertension had no effect on the quality of life of the patients.

Conclusion: The quality of life among stroke survivors in this study, was above average. Spousal support, higher educational qualification, ischemic stroke, were positively associated with good quality of life of stroke survivors

More Information

How to cite this article: Daniel-Amadi UC, Ojule IN, Adeniji FO. Determinants of Post Stroke Quality of Life: Experiences from a Physiotherapy Unit Clinic, South-South, Nigeria. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(1):69-79.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(1).11

Keywords:

Stroke,
quality of life,
SIS 3.0.

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in our locality. This study adds to the growing body of research on QOL among stroke survivors within the country. This result will also minimize the gap in evidence-based research on the quality of life of stroke patients, particularly in the South-South region of the Nigeria.

Introduction

Non-Communicable diseases continue to assume increasing importance in both developed and developing countries. They have been described as impairments of bodily structure and function that necessitate a modification of the person's normal life over an extended period of time. Stroke is a very common non-communicable disease (NCD) especially among people of African descent anywhere in the world [2]. Current stroke outcome assessments are often limited to the resulting neurological impairment and functional disability. This thrust neglects to evaluate the total influence the event has on a survivor's well-being quality of life (QoL) [3]. Studies on QoL necessitated the paradigm shift of the concept of adding life to years against previous orientation of adding years to life. The impact of stroke on the life of an individual is multi-faceted, affecting a wide range of functions including physical, mental, emotional and social aspects of a survivor's life [4,5, 6]. Studying QoL of stroke survivors provides insights on personal and communal consequences of stroke and also facilitates the development of a more holistic patient-centered approach in the management of stroke [7]. Furthermore, QoL studies enable the identification of challenges stroke patients deal with, some which may not be health related but have great bearing on their daily lives. Information from this study can be used to educate the general public, families and stroke survivors on common deficits among stroke survivors thereby helping them understand and adjust to the outcome of the illness and management [8].

The studies reporting quality of life of stroke survivors are replete in Europe and America [10], but scarce in low- and middle- income counties [11] where 70% of the 50 million global stroke survivors are found. Overall, when compared to high-income countries, stroke tends to occur in younger populations in Africans [12,13] occurring at a younger mean age of 57 years compared to 66.0 years in high-income countries. Also, studies of the last four decades indicate that stroke incidence in high-income countries has declined by over 40% whereas low- and middle-income countries such as Nigeria have witnessed a double increment in incidence in the same time period, [16].

This study aimed to assess the quality of life of stroke survivors in Nigeria, understand the domains that are usually most affected and factors that determine good quality of life in order to generate information that may enable clinicians, care-givers and rehabilitation experts

assist survivors return to normal or near normal life [17].

Materials and Methods

Study Participants

In this descriptive cross-sectional study, 122 adult patients who had been evaluated and diagnosed as having had a stroke and recovering were recruited while undergoing physical rehabilitation at two tertiary hospitals in South-South Nigeria. Stroke patients who had suffered a transient ischemic heart attack, recurrent persistent deficit, underlying mental disorders and those who were handicapped before the stroke event were excluded. Also excluded were stroke patients with gross cognitive impairment. The study was approved by the Ethics and Research Committee of the two hospitals (UPH/CEREMAD/REC/MM61/066).

Data Collection

Data were collected during their physiotherapy sessions. Two tools were used. A semi-structured questionnaire that captured socio-demographics (age, religion, gender, educational qualification, income, marital status, employment status and residential area). Also captured - clinical history (type of stroke, duration, side of hemiparesis, dominant hand, comorbidities) and lastly, at home care and follow-up visits (primary care giver, who pays for the cost of care, distance to and from the hospital, presence or absence of assistive devices at home). The second tool was the World Health Organization's Stroke Impact Scale (SIS 3.0) [18] which was used to measure the quality of life among stroke survivors. SIS 3.0 is a self-report, stroke-specific quality of life outcome measure, consisting of 59 questions grouped into eight domains: strength, hand function, mobility, activities of daily living, emotion, memory, communication and social participation. Level of difficulty experienced by the patient while evaluating each domain is rated using a five-point Likert scale. The 8 domains were grouped into the three composites of quality of life (physical, mental and social). Strength, hand function, activities of daily living (ADL), and mobility were aggregated to create a composite "Physical domain." Mental health was measured by two domains: memory as it relates to memory loss or the amount of difficulty in remembering things while emotion was tied to the frequency of events. The remaining two domains: communication and social participation measured social health. An additional section assessed perception of recovery. The scores were from 0 to 100 (where 0 score means no recovery/no improvement and 100 meaning full recovery); hence the higher scores

indicate the better health related quality of life (HRQoL). A satisfactory responsiveness data (minimal detectable change and minimal clinically important difference) have been reported for some domains of the measure. [19,20]. The tool can be completed in 15 minutes. It has excellent predictive and constructive validity [21,22]. Its internal consistency and inter-rater reliability have also been assessed and found to be satisfactory [18]

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0. The socioeconomic, demographic, clinical and follow-up visit variables of the respondents were summarized with descriptive statistics and presented as percentages. Analysis of variance (ANOVA one-way test) was used to determine how the socio-demographic, clinical and follow-up visit variables affect the quality of life. Pearson correlation analysis was used to assess the correlation between specific socio-demographic variables and the 8 domains of the SIS 3.0. Correlations were considered weak for values less than 0.30, moderate for values from 0.30 - 0.59, and strong for values 0.60 or greater. Chi square was employed in understanding the effect of clinical factors on the 8 domains of the SIS 3.0, while linear regression assessed the relationship between the follow-up variables and the domains of quality of life. Alpha level was set at equals to or less than 0.05 for all the analyses.

Results

A total of 122 patients (67 men and 55 women), participated in this study. The Socio-demographics of the patients are shown in Table 1. The mean age (in years) of respondents was 59.0(±9.12) with age range 27-74years. The highest percentage of respondents (54%) fall within the age group 56-65years. Majority of the participants were married (87%). Most of the participants had some form of formal education except for two persons (1%). Thirty-three percent (33%) of the participants did not have enough income. There were more male participants (55%). The commoner stroke sub-type (70%) was infarction stroke, with majority of them having had the stroke for over 12 months (77%). A little lower than half had had a previous stroke with majority having co-morbid hypertension (88%) and diabetes (64%). Less than half (47%) of the participants had their right hands affected by the stroke. Almost half of them (47%) had their spouses as their primary caregiver, followed by their children (33%). The hospital bill of more than half of them was taken care of by their family (61%). Majority of them did not use modern

assistive devices at home (60%) and were always treated with respect at home (60%).

Table 1: Summary of Socio-Demographic, Clinical and Home Care Profiles

Variables	Frequency (n =122)	Percent (%)
Age (years)		
26-35	5	3
36-45	4	3
46-55	24	19
56-65	64	54
66-75	25	21
Mean Age (in years): 59.0 (±9.12)		
Male	67	55
Marital Status		
Married	105	87
Education		
Higher education	91	75
None	2	1
Clinical Factors		
Type of stroke		
Infarction	84	70
Commonly affected Hand		
Right	57	47
Previous stroke		
No	66	54
Diabetes		
Yes	85	70
Hypertension		
Yes	106	88
Home care		
Primary care giver		
Spouse	55	47
Hospital bill		
Family	72	61
Treated with respect		
Always	73	61
Modern assistive devices		
No	73	61

Table 2 shows data for the SIS sub-scales. The proportion of the average raw score to the total raw score of all the domains and total quality of life score were all above 50%. In comparison, the emotions domain had the highest proportion of average to highest possible scores (91%). Strength domain had the overall lowest average score (12.3), possible score (20) and proportion of average to highest score (60).

Table 2: Proportion of Average SIS3.0 Scores to Highest Possible Scores

	Average Raw Score	Highest Possible Score	Proportion of Average to Highest Possible Scores (%)
Strength	12.3	20	60

Memory	23.4	35	69
Emotions	29.9	33	91
Communication	23.9	35	68
ADL	30.8	50	62
Mobility	28.0	45	62
Hand Affected	14.7	25	60
Social Participation	23.7	40	60
Total SIS Scores	187.9	283	66

Table 3 details the analysis of variance (ANOVA) between demographic factors, socioeconomic factors, clinical factors, and home care on the quality of life of the stroke participants. Age (F = 4.9(P <0.001) and marital status (F = 4.28(P <0.007) had significant influence on the quality of life, gender (F=3.54(P <0.070) and employment status (F = 4.28; P <0.137) did not. Diabetes and hypertension had no effect on the

quality of life of the patients but the side of lesion (F=8.17; P <0.005), having a previous stroke (F=8,08(P <0.005) and the type of stroke (F = 11.37; P <0.001) were strongly associated with the quality of life. All aspects of the at home care with the exception of the hospital payment (F=1.73;L P <0.165) affected the quality of life significantly.

Table 3. One way ANOVA between Demographics, Socioeconomic, Clinical Factors and Home Care and Quality of Life (SIS 3.0) at P < 0.05

Variables	STROKE IMPACT SCALE 3.0	
	F	P
Demographics		
Age	4.93	<0.001
Gender	3.54	0.070
Socioeconomic		
Employment	1.88	0.137
Marital status	4.28	0.007
Education	3.33	0.003
Clinical Factors		
Duration of stroke	0.001	0.976
Type of stroke	11.37	0.001
Side of brain lesion	8.17	0.005
Previous stroke	3.56	0.062
Diabetes	0.49	0.484
Hypertension	1.43	0.234
Home care		
Primary care giver	6.15	<0.001
Treated with respect	17.00	<0.001
Assistive devices	39.78	<0.001
Hospital bill	1.73	0.165

Table 4. Association between Socio-Demographic Variables and Quality of Life Domains at P= < 0.05

	Age r (p)	gender r (p)	Marital status r (p)	Employment status r (p)	Education qualification r (p)
Strength	-0.33(<0.001)	0.09(0.311)	0.26(0.005)	-0.19(0.049)	0.1(0.913)
Memory	-0.23(0.013)	0.14(0.128)	0.15(0.109)	-0.12(0.194)	0.13(0.156)
Emotions	-0.43(<0.001)	0.11(0.232)	0.21(0.023)	-0.29(0.002)	0.07(0.415)
Communication	-0.15(0.090)	0.10(0.304)	0.09(0.310)	-0.15(0.126)	0.11(0.226)
ADL	-0.189(0.037)	0.13(0.163)	0.24(0.009)	-0.20(0.038)	0.07(0.443)
Mobility	-0.16(0.071)	0.11(0.243)	0.13(0.154)	-0.02(0.821)	0.10(0.254)
Hand Affected	-0.35(<0.001)	0.11(0.242)	0.184(0.043)	-0.15(0.126)	-0.07(0.474)

Social Participation	-0.38(<0.001)	0.07(0.461)	0.21(0.020)	-0.09(0.373)	0.04(0.628)
Recovery Self Assessment	-0.28(0.002)	0.14(0.137)	0.27(0.003)	-0.13(0.157)	0.04(0.696)
Total S.I.S Scores	-0.37(<0.001)	0.17(0.070)	0.25(0.007)	-0.14(0.133)	0.08(0.400)

Pearson’s correlation between socio-demographic factors and the domains of quality of life (table 4) portrays a negative correlation between age and all SIS domains except communication (r = -0.15; p = 0.090) and mobility (r = -0.16; p = 0.071). Gender and educational level had no impact on the QOL domains. Marital status affected strength (r = 0.26; p = 0.005),

emotion (r = 0.21; p = 0.023), ADL (r = 0.24; p = 0.009), hand affected (r = 0.184; p = 0.043), social participation (r = 0.21; p = 0.020) and recovery self-assessment (r = 0.27; p = 0.003). Employment status affected only strength (r = 0.19; p = 0.049) , emotions (r = 0.29; p = 0.002) and ADL domains (r = -0.20; p = 0.038).

Table 5a: Chi-Square Association of Independence: Quality of Life (Physical Component) and Clinical Status

Physical Component (Strength, Hand function, ADL and Mobility)				X ²	P=< 0.05	
Clinical factors		LOW QOL	MEDIUM QOL			HIGH QOL
Duration	<12mth	0(0%)	23(85%)	4(15%)	12.977	0.002
	12mth	17(18%)	45(47%)	33(35%)		
Type Of Stroke	Infarction	6(7%)	49(58%)	29(35%)	10.819	0.004
	Hemorrhage	11(29%)	19(50%)	8(21%)		
Limb Affected	Left	13(19%)	36(54%)	18(27%)	3.884	0.143
	Right	4(7%)	32(58%)	19(35%)		
Previous Stroke	Yes	9(15%)	34(58%)	16(27%)	0.604	0.739
	No	8(13%)	34(54%)	21(33%)		
Diabetes	Yes	14(18%)	36(47%)	27(35%)	7.271	0.026
	No	3(7%)	32(71%)	10(22%)		
Hypertension	Yes	14(13%)	64(60%)	26(27%)	6.029	0.049
	No	3(20%)	4(27%)	8(53%)		

Further analysis of the impact of clinical factors on QoL Domains was done with chi-square association of independence. Majority of those with time since stroke of less than 12 months (85.2%) had the physical component of their quality of life moderately affected negatively. A little over half of the ischemic stroke participants (58.3%) and half of the haemorrhagic stroke participants (50.0%) experienced moderate negative

changes in their physical quality of life. Less than half of those who had diabetes (47%) experienced moderate difficulty in their physical quality of life while 60.0% of stroke survivors with hypertension had moderate difficulty in this area of quality of life. The limb affected and a previous stroke had no significant negative change on their physical component.

Table 5b: Chi-Square Association of Independence: Quality Of Life (Mental Component) and Clinical Status

Clinical factors		Mental Component		X ²	P =<0.05
		High	Low		
Time Since Stroke	<12mth	0(0%)	27(100%)	10.812	0.001
	12MTH	29(30%)	66(70%)		
Limb Affected	Left	12(18%)	55(82%)	2.817	0.093
	RIGHT	17(31%)	38(69 %)		
Hemiparesis	Left	19(32%)	41(68%)	4.062	0.044
	RIGHT	10(16%)	52(84%)		
Previous Stroke	Yes		45(76%)	0.000	0.992
	No	15(24%)	48(76%)		
Diabetes	Yes	17(22%)	60(78%)	0.330	0.566
	No	12(27%)	33(73%)		
Hypertension	Yes	21(20%)	86(80%)	8.249	0.004
	No	8(53%)	7(47%)		

Time since stroke and the presence of co-morbid hypertension were the only clinical factors with significant changes in mental quality of life. All participants with time since stroke less than 12 months experienced mild impact changes in the mental aspect of their quality of life and two thirds of those 12 months and above (69.5%) also experienced the same level of impact in their mental quality of life. 80% of all

participants with hypertension also noticed minimal changes to their mental quality of life. Majority of participants in two categories of time since stroke, limb affected and hemiparesis experienced mild changes in their social quality of life. Changes due to previous stroke, diabetes, hypertension and mental of quality of life were not significant at $p=0.05$.

Table 5c: Chi-Square Association Of Independence: Relationship between Quality of Life (Social Component) And Clinical Status

SOCIAL COMPONENT				X ²	P =<0.05
Clinical factors		HIGH	LOW		
Time Since Stroke	<12mth	3(11%)	24(89%)	6.935	0.008
	12MTH	36(38%)	59(62%)		
Pathology	Infarction	32(38%)	57(62%)	4.657	0.031
	Hemorrhage	7(18%)	31(82%)		
Limb Affected	Left	14(21%)	53(79%)	8.377	0.004
	Right	25(45%)	30(55%)		
Previous Stroke	Yes	17(29%)	42(71%)	0.522	0.470
	No	22(35%)	41(65%)		
Diabetes	Yes	24(31 %)	53(69%)	0.061	0.805
	No	15(33%)	30(67%)		
Hypertension	Yes	33(31%)	74(69%)	0.507	0.476
	No	6(40%)	9(60%)		

Table 6: Linear Regression of Relationship between Home Care, Disability and Quality of Life

Quality of Life (R)					P= 0.05
Home Care	Total S.I.S	Physical	Mental	Social	
Caregiver	0.384	0.407	0.407	0.269	<0.001
Assistive Devices	0.502	0.485	0.338	0.521	<0.001
Treated with Respect	0.332	0.197	0.363a	0.521	<0.001

Linear regression was used to measure association between factors of home care and the three components of quality of life with significance level set at $p \leq 0.05$ (Table 6). Use of Caregivers moderately affected the physical and mental aspects of quality of life positively ($R = 0.407$ and $R = 0.407$ respectively). Assistive devices and treated with respect also had positive impact on the social aspect of quality of life by ($R = 0.521$), while treated with respect had very low association with the physical quality of life ($R = 0.197$).

Discussion

Quality of life is a concept that has become fundamental to life and living of all individuals irrespective of morbidity status [23], hence, the recent emphasis on “adding life to years” instead of the traditional efforts at “adding years to life” The consequences of stroke on survivors affect their physical, mental and social well-being and has given rise to the need to understand the trajectory of stroke on the quality of life of survivors. In the current study, there were 122 participants, majority of them male,

corresponding with most stroke studies [24,25], mean age was 59.0(±9s.12) years. The mean age of the respondents in the study is similar to that obtained in a Turkish study [26], and some other parts of Nigeria [27,28,24]. Most of the participants were within the age group 56-60 years. This age group is still within the productive age group. What we observed was stroke occurring earlier, in a younger age range unlike in high income countries where stroke is noted to be more prevalent in persons aged 66 and above [13]. More than half of the respondents had ischemic stroke as was commonly reported in other studies [29,30]. The study identified spouses as the primary care givers, closely followed by children and their hospital bills were footed by members of their families. Children were more often relied upon to bring them to the hospital and many of them were treated with respect at home. This is a pointer to good family support and cohesion that is a cultural trend in Nigeria. The use of assistive devices was less common due mainly to availability of family and community supports.

The importance of QOL as an outcome measure after a stroke cannot be over emphasized as it brings an extensive detail of the impact of illness on various facets of an individual's life rather than just focussing on the level of decrepitude [11]. Results from this study, show that the quality of life among stroke survivors was above average (Table 2). This does not align with previous studies that have reported reduced perception of quality of life among stroke survivors [11, 24, 31, 32].

Our study noted that age correlated negatively with QOL, implying that QOL decreases with advancing age, a finding consistent with several previous studies [25,29,33,34]. On the flip side, some other studies identified younger age to correlate with a lower quality of life for stroke survivors [11,35]. There were also studies [25,36,37] that observed no significant influence of age on QOL. The results of this study showed that gender had no significant influence on the quality of life. Other previous studies [36,37,40,41] also came to the same conclusion that gender had no effect on the QOL of stroke survivors. However, in some other studies [11,42, 43], it was found that being female was significantly associated with poorer QOL ($p < 0.001$). Badaru et al attributed the variation in the results to differences in the populations and the domains of QOL investigated [44]. We have attributed the variation to differences in settings such as the culture of the people and other socio-economic differences.

The presence of spousal support and other social relationships (children, brothers, sisters, friends, neighbours), contribute significantly to improved quality of life of stroke survivors [45]. Our current study also showed a significant positive association between family cohesion and quality of life. Two separate studies in Nigeria [25,27], reported that being married and having spousal support were significantly correlated with better QOL. Social support is also important in improving motivation to restore independency of an individual who hitherto had been apparently healthy and suddenly becomes totally dependent as a result of a stroke [25]. The result mirrors our local society in that we have strong family and communal bonds.

Higher educational qualification as we observed in this study related positively to good quality of life. Similar findings in other studies [47,48,49]. A higher level of education have been documented [25,48] to equip people to handle numerous challenges of life. A study from the northern part of Nigerian by Abubakar & Isezuo [24], did not observe any influence of the educational status on the QOL of stroke survivors.

When we looked at the contribution of the employment status of the respondents after the stroke on their quality of life. We observed no relationship. This contrasted with the findings from other studies

that reported a reduced QOL with unemployment after stroke [11,25,51,52,53].

Gbiri *et al.* [33] carried out post-stroke QOL three to six months after the event and observed that patients with haemorrhagic stroke had a better QOL than those with ischemic stroke. However the results from this study show that more respondents with ischemic stroke had better QOL in the physical aspects than those with haemorrhagic subtype. But there are other studies that found no significant association between stroke type and QOL [54,55].

The influence of time since stroke on QOL was negligible, a finding that is at variance with most studies reviewed [11,56,57]. There are several factors that could have contributed to the observation in this study. First, the participants were recruited from a rehabilitation centre which showed they were receiving on-going active care. Secondly, the tertiary hospital environment where rehabilitation was taking place conferred some advantage in that other clinics and specialty consultations could be easily accessed by the patient. The presence of hypertension and diabetes in stroke survivors were not significantly associated with poorer health satisfaction scores in the current study. Again they are being rehabilitated in a tertiary health facility where other co-morbidities could be handled. This is not in sync with some other studies. This finding contradicts the observations of other endeavours that showed stroke survivors with multiple comorbidities to have poorer QOL [11,58,59]. Anecdotally, the presence of serious co-morbidity like diabetes mellitus and hypertension is expected to cause a downward trend in the recovery and QOL of a stroke survivor. Further studies therefore, are needed to understand the reason behind our finding. The aforementioned result of our study tallied with a Korean report by Jeon *et al* [47]. In their study, most of the comorbidities, except cardiovascular diseases, had no statistically significant association with HR-QOL of stroke survivors.

According to our result, a previous stroke had no statistical connection to the QOL of stroke survivors. This finding aligns with some other previous studies [11, 59]. Regarding the limb affected and QOL, variations abound globally. Findings from this study, showed that this variable, affected only the social component. It is quite surprising to learn that limb affected didn't have an impact on the physical component of QOL as was expected. This may be because the stroke event affected the left limb in majority of the participants. Most Nigerians are right-handed and it is safe to assume that majority of these participants are right handed as this was not measured. Therefore, the participants are able to do so many things with their right hands. This finding disagrees with the report that left limb affectations were significantly

associated with poorer QOL and overall health outlook [11,25]. Other studies have either reported the reverse or absence of a relationship between stroke site and HR-QOL [54].

From the results of this study, having modern assistive devices had a moderate effect on the total and different components of quality of life of the stroke survivors (Table 6), especially the social aspects of quality of life. This aligns with earlier citations [60,61].

Conclusion

Quality of life was above average across the eight domains and it was highest in the emotional domain showing good emotional health. Spousal support, higher educational qualification, ischemic stroke, were positively associated with good quality of life of stroke survivors in our locality. The role of quality of life assessment as a major objective in public health, cannot be overstated, as it is a relevant needs assessment tool and also as an outcome measure in health promotion interventions.

This study adds to the growing body of research on QOL among stroke survivors within the country, thereby minimizing the gap in evidence-based research on the quality of life of stroke patients, particularly the South-South region of Nigeria.

Authors' Contributions

All the authors contributed in producing the work. All the authors read and approved the final copy.

Conflict of Interest

No competing interest exists.

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